

ML-Aided 2D Indoor Positioning Using Energy Harvesters and Optical Detectors for Self Powered Light-based IoT Sensors

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Abstract—Advancements in 6G and IoT sensor networks prioritise sustainability and energy efficiency, with positioning services essential for improved functionality. Light-based IoT (LIoT) systems present a promising solution by achieving energy autonomy through Photovoltaic (PV) energy harvesting and enabling Visible Light Communication (VLC) via indoor luminaries as Optical Access Points (OAP). This research explores the repurposing of energy harvesters at LIoT nodes and detectors at OAPs for positioning and orientation detection in energy-autonomous, battery-free, intermittently operating LIoT sensor networks. We propose potential node and OAP designs, validated by proof-of-concept prototypes, utilising conventional Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to enhance localisation. Performance evaluations demonstrate 80% positioning accuracy within 12.5 cm tolerance and 68% orientation prediction accuracy. This approach allows LIoT devices to communicate, harvest energy, and determine their position and orientation using the same illumination from OAPs, underscoring the potential of this LIoT-based system as a sustainable solution for next-generation IoT sensors.

Index Terms—Visible light communication, Indoor positioning, Machine learning, Battery-free IoT, Sustainable sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability and energy efficiency are essential Key Performance Indicators (KPI) in the advancement of 6G networks [1], [2]. In the context of Internet of Things (IoT) systems, these KPIs can be enhanced through design concepts such as zero-energy, battery-free, and energy-harvesting approaches, along with the use of sustainable electronic technologies, including printed and biodegradable electronics [3], [4]. These advancements enable the development of low-cost, compact, low-maintenance, and environmentally friendly sensing devices that are seamlessly integrated into sectors such as logistics, healthcare, industrial automation, and environmental monitoring, thereby improving quality of service while promoting sustainability [5], [6]. Moreover, to further enhance sustainability, the Light-based IoT (LIoT) exploits license-free optical spectrum for communication, demonstrating ways in

which indoor illumination can serve dual purposes: enabling data communication through Visible Light Communication (VLC) and powering battery-free IoT sensing nodes via Photovoltaic (PV) Energy Harvesting (EH). In LIoT systems, highly energy-constrained nodes operate intermittently using harvested energy, supported by energy-aware protocols, while energy-unconstrained indoor illumination sources serve as Optical Access Points (OAPs). These OAPs handle complex computations and are equipped with infrared optical signal receivers to receive uplink data from the LIoT sensor nodes [7]–[9].

Moving toward 6G, positioning and location services are expected to become fundamental system elements, driven by the demand for low-cost tracking and high-accuracy industrial applications, not only in outdoor but also in indoor environments [10]. Visible Light Positioning (VLP) offers a sustainable localisation solution by utilising indoor illumination through approaches such as triangulation, fingerprinting, and proximity-based methods. Machine Learning (ML) techniques such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Deep Neural Networks (DNN), k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), decision trees, random forests, and Support Vector Machines (SVM) have been widely explored for indoor localisation, proving particularly effective in enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of VLP systems [11]–

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[14]. These models improve accuracy, reduce estimation time, and mitigate noise and interference, thereby optimising VLP for real-world scenarios.

The concept of 'Energy Harvesters as Sensors' (EHAAS) discusses the approach of re-purposing energy harvesters to function as sensors, further enhancing design optimisation and sustainability [15]. Battery-free IoT technologies, such as LIoT systems, rely on components such as energy harvesters and detectors, which are typically dedicated to specific functions. However, the potential to re-purpose these components for additional functionalities, such as indoor localisation, can further increase the sustainability and efficiency of the system.

Building upon our prior work [16] on ML-based indoor localisation for battery-free, energy-autonomous LIoT systems, this study takes major steps further by introducing a twofold contribution. First, we propose a combined approach to re-purpose PV energy harvesters at the node and Optical Signal Detectors (OSD) at the OAP to enhance 2D indoor positioning accuracy. Second, we extend the scope beyond 2D positioning by presenting a novel method for estimating the orientation of the LIoT node. This research aims to enhance positioning accuracy and enable orientation awareness in battery-free, intermittently operating LIoT systems by estimating node localisation at the OAP, thereby offloading complex computations from energy-constrained LIoT nodes. By using ML algorithms, the proposed approach repurposes integrated system components to achieve enhanced indoor positioning and orientation determination efficiently and sustainably. This research addresses the critical gap in positioning and orientation solutions for energy-harvesting-based, intermittently operating, battery-free devices. The proposed method is particularly advantageous in densely node deployed environments such as supermarkets, healthcare facilities, and military settings, where indoor illumination is available, and concerns about Radio Frequency (RF) interference and security exist. The enhanced localisation awareness can significantly improve the quality of service in application environments. Furthermore, the integration of spatial awareness within the LIoT network enhances functionalities such as internode networking [9], addressing challenges posed by the Line-of-Sight (LOS) nature of Optical Wireless Communication (OWC) in LIoT systems.

The contributions of this work are as follows:

- 1) Presenting the re-purposing of OSDs and energy harvesters in LIoT systems to enable enhanced indoor 2D positioning with orientation awareness.
- 2) Proposing and developing novel LIoT node and OAP designs to address the absence of off-the-shelf battery-free platforms, enabling the prototyping and validation of the proposed localisation concept.
- 3) Demonstrating and validating the proposed system's performance through hardware prototype implementation, achieving accuracy within a 12.5 cm tolerance and 68% orientation prediction.

The rest of the article is organised as follows: Section II presents the state of the art and related works; Section III introduces the model of the proposed system; Section IV details the prototype implementation used for evaluation; Section V

Fig. 1. Scenario of a sustainable LIoT sensor network integrated into consumable-attached smart labels, positioned under an OAP that provides primary illumination for the indoor environment.

provides the performance evaluation; and the conclusion is presented in Section VI.

II. STATE OF ART AND RELATED WORKS

PV energy harvesters have been explored for dual use in indoor VLP and EH for IoT systems, promoting efficiency and sustainability. The research in [17] discusses the use of PV cells for positioning based on the angle of arrival of visible light, employing a quadrant solar cell and a third-order Ridge Regression ML (RRML) algorithm to improve accuracy. In [18], a 2D localisation approach for IoT nodes in Li-Ion battery-based LoRaWAN networks is explored, by using PV energy harvesters for both localisation and energy autonomy by measuring PV cell currents to estimate positioning. In order to address the research gap in indoor localisation approaches for PV EH based, battery-free, intermittently operating, and highly energy-constrained IoT nodes, our previous work [16] introduced an indoor localisation approach for LIoT systems inherently possessing these characteristics. In this approach, voltage readings from multiple distinctively oriented PV cells integrated into an LIoT sensor node were utilised to predict 2D position using traditional ML algorithms, achieving 80% positioning accuracy within a 20 cm tolerance. Our previous work also demonstrated that LIoT nodes can simultaneously communicate, harvest energy, and perform localisation using the same illumination source while operating energy autonomously.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed localisation method for LIoT nodes exploits distinct illumination patterns on the node's surface and the direction of signal arrival at the OAP. Fig. 1 illustrates a scenario of this system model.

A. Optical Access Point and Node Architecture for IIoT Networks

In a typical IIoT node network environment, the illumination sources are expected to act as centralised OAP by modulating light for communication while providing illumination for energising the nodes. The nodes are expected to have surface-integrated optical transceivers for uplink and downlink data communication and PV cells on multiple surfaces to enhance EH performance. On the other hand, OAP utilise multi-directional OSD to receive the incoming data from the directional optical transmitter on the nodes.

1) *Repurposability of OAP Optical Signal Detectors for Localisation*: As shown in Fig. 1, when considering uplink from Node 1 to detector RX1, The effective collection area of such directional detector, $A_{\text{eff}}(\beta)$, is given by [19]:

$$A_{\text{eff}}(\beta) = \begin{cases} Af(\beta)g(\beta) \cos \beta, & 0 \leq \beta \leq \beta_c \\ 0, & \beta > \beta_c, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where A is the physical area of the detector, β is the angle of incidence of the incoming optical signal with respect to the normal to the detector's surface. $f(\beta)$ and $g(\beta)$ denote the optical filter gain and the concentrator gain respectively, and β_c is the critical angle defining the detector's Field of View (FOV). For angles $0 \leq \beta \leq \beta_c$, the effective collection area decreases proportionally to $\cos \beta$, signifying that the detector's capacity to collect optical signals diminishes as the angle of incidence increases. For $\beta > \beta_c$, the effective area becomes zero, implying that each detector has a region in which it can effectively collect optical signals. Furthermore, in indoor environments where optical data or energy is transmitted over short distances utilising a Lambertian light source such as an LED, the optical path loss can be described by the following equation [20]:

$$L = \frac{(m+1)A}{2\pi d_t^2} \cos^m(\alpha) \cos(\beta), \quad (2)$$

where m denotes the Lambertian order, d_t is the distance between the LED and the detector, α represents the optical transmitter's irradiance angle, and β is the incidence angle at the detector, considering the uplink communication. Based on this equation, by analysing the received optical signal intensity and the orientation of the detector, both the distance and the Direction of Arrival (DoA) of the signal can be determined. This information allows for the estimation of the node's location at the OAP by correlating the signal strength with the directionality of the incoming signal. Therefore, based on the layout in Fig. 1, OSD RX1 and RX4 are expected to primarily detect the optical signal from Node 1, while OSD RX2 and RX3 are expected to predominantly detect the signal from Node 2.

2) *Repurposability of Node PV energy harvesters for Localisation*: As shown in Fig. 1, based on the orientation and location of each node indoors, the PV-integrated surfaces exhibit different OAP illumination patterns across the surfaces of the nodes. For Node 1, surfaces such as S4 and S3 are well-illuminated compared to the non-illuminated surfaces S1 and S2. Similarly, for Node 2, surfaces S1 and S2 receive better

illumination compared to S4 and S3. In addition, due to the reflection, the S4 surface of Node 2 is slightly illuminated compared to the non-illuminated surfaces of Node 1. This demonstrates that the OAP illumination over the PV-integrated surfaces varies depending on the location of the node. Each PV-integrated surface generates a voltage corresponding to the level of illumination it receives, as expressed in the following equation [21]:

$$V_{\text{OC}} = \frac{bkT}{q} \ln(I) + C, \quad (3)$$

where V_{OC} is the open-circuit voltage, C is a fitting parameter, I represents the intensity, b is the ideality factor, q is the elementary charge, T is the temperature, and k denotes the Boltzmann constant. Therefore, the voltage on each differently illuminated integrated PV surfaces can be expected as [16]:

$$V_{DI} > V_{SI} > V_{NI}, \quad (4)$$

where V_{DI} represents the voltage on well-illuminated PV surfaces, V_{SI} represents the voltage on slightly illuminated PV surfaces, and V_{NI} represents the voltage on non-illuminated PV surfaces. Furthermore, considering the data downlink and the energy link from the OAP to Node 2, the received optical power on the PV surfaces can be expressed by the following equation [20]:

$$P_r = (H_{\text{los}}(0) + H_{\text{nlos}}(0)) P_t, \quad (5)$$

where P_t is the transmitted power, $H_{\text{los}}(0)$ is the channel gain for the line-of-sight component, and $H_{\text{nlos}}(0)$ is the channel gain for the non-line-of-sight components.

The channel gain for the LOS component, H_{LOS} , can be expressed by [20]:

$$H_{\text{LOS}} = \frac{n+1}{2\pi} \frac{A}{d_r^2} \rho \cos^n(\phi_d) T_s(\psi_d) g(\psi_d) \cos(\psi), \quad (6)$$

where n is the order of Lambertian emission, A is the receiver area, d_r is the distance between the transmitter and receiver, ρ is the reflectance, ϕ_d is the irradiance angle, $T_s(\psi_d)$ is the gain of the optical filter, $g(\psi_d)$ is the gain of the optical concentrator, and ψ is the angle of incidence.

The channel gain for the NLOS component, H_{NLOS} , is given by [20]:

$$H_{\text{NLOS}} = \frac{n+1}{2\pi} \frac{A}{d_{r1} d_{r2}} \rho \cos^n(\phi_r) dA_{\text{ref}} \cos(\lambda) \cos(\gamma) \times T_s(\psi_d) g(\psi_d) \cos(\psi_r), \quad (7)$$

where ϕ_r is the irradiance angle for the NLOS path, d_{r1} is the distance between the OAP and the reflective point, d_{r2} is the distance between the reflective point and the PV cell at the node, dA_{ref} is the reflective element on the wall, λ is the angle related to the reflection, γ is the angle related to the incident direction on the reflecting surface, and ψ_r is the angle of incidence for the NLOS path.

Therefore, based on 3 and 4, it can be observed that the variation in the voltage of the integrated PV cells on the node can be used to estimate the relative location and orientation of the node with respect to the OAP. Additionally,

Fig. 2. Proposed structures for LIoT positioning enabled system. (a) Node with n number of multi-surface integrated PV cells. (b) OAP with m OSD for receiving signals and determining the direction of arrival.

according to 6 and 7, the received optical power decreases with increasing distance in both LOS and NLOS scenarios. Hence, by analysing the voltage variations of the integrated PV cells on each surface of the node, a distance estimate can be obtained. By transmitting these PV voltage measurements to the OAP and combining them with the OAP detector-based information discussed earlier, the indoor positioning of the LIoT nodes relative to the OAP can be estimated. By utilising ML approaches with a power-unrestricted OAP, the impact of external factors such as noise and temperature can be minimised, thereby enhancing position accuracy.

B. Proposed structure of the LIoT node and OAP

In order to repurpose energy harvesters for localisation while preserving typical LIoT node functions, the proposed node structure is illustrated in Fig. 2a. Based on the Harvest-Store-Use (HSU) EH protocol from previous designs [7]–[9], the structure divides localisation functionality into two parts: the Energy Harvesting Unit (EHU) and associated circuitry. The EHU includes PV energy harvesters, energy storage, and power management, optimised with Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT). The circuitry handles sensing, processing, and communication through a Micro-Controller Unit (MCU), optical transceivers, and application-specific sensors and actuators. Additionally, to enable localisation by measuring multi-surface integrated PV cells with minimal impact on the EH process, a switching circuit and probe connect these PV cells to the MCU's ADC, maintaining suitable voltage and current levels while minimising disruptions to EH performance.

The proposed structure of the OAP, developed based on previous works [7], [8], is depicted in Fig. 2b. The OAP mainly consists of a controller unit and a communication unit. The controller unit performs all calculations related to the proposed localisation estimation algorithms, processes the commands and received data, manages the nodes under the coverage,

and modulates the LEDs using an LED driver, all while maintaining indoor-friendly illumination levels. The communication unit includes LEDs, which serve as both illumination sources and data/energy providers for the LIoT nodes, along with multi-directional OSD for receiving signals from various directions. Each detector comprises a photo-diode, a band-pass filter, and an amplifier to filter noise and amplify the signal for demodulation and decoding. Additionally, to repurpose OSD for LIoT positioning, all OSD are connected in parallel, allowing the control unit to individually measure parameters such as the received signal intensity and identify the DOA.

C. Machine Learning at OAP

The proposed 2D positioning approach can employ a two-stage method that combines conventional models with DNN to improve accuracy in determining the position and orientation of a node. The ML model at the OAP can proceed with inference and to then determine the LIoT node's position based on the readings from multi-PV cells at the node and multi-OSD at the OAP, which correlates with the node's location and orientation. The OAP can utilise its unrestricted power for energy-intensive tasks, such as data pre-processing and ML model training, while offloading lower-power tasks such as inference to battery-less, power-constrained LIoT nodes [16].

1) *Stage 1: Euclidean Distance Estimation*: In this stage, conventional ML models can be used to estimate the Euclidean Distance (ED) between the LIoT node and the OAP. The ED between two points i and j in an M -dimensional space is given by [11]

$$d_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{m=1}^M (p_{m,i}^{on} - P_{m,j})^2}, \quad (8)$$

where, $p_{m,i}^{on}$ and $P_{m,j}$ are the coordinates of points i and j in the m -th dimension, respectively. This ED metric provides a straightforward way to assess how accurately the ML models could predict the positions of the measurement points relative to the known center of the OAP. The objective of this stage is to achieve highly accurate ED predictions, which can serve as an additional feature in the subsequent stage for precise positioning. In order to predict the ED from a node to an OAP, Mutual Information (MI) scores of normalised PV voltage and OSD readings are utilised to assess feature relevance [22]. MI effectively identifies the most significant features, facilitating the selection of appropriate ML models. Regression models capable of capturing both linear and nonlinear relationships are considered suitable for predicting ED. The following regression ML models can be identified as applicable for this purpose:

- 1) Linear Regression (LR): If the distance estimation shows a primarily linear relationship between inputs and the target distance, LR can serve as a fast and interpretable baseline model.
- 2) Decision Tree (DT): A non-linear model that works effectively for capturing intricate patterns in smaller datasets. The DT model splits data based on feature thresholds, which could work effectively if the distance varies in a threshold-based manner with certain features.

- 3) Random Forest (RandF): This ensemble-based model can capture complex patterns and is particularly useful if there are nonlinear relationships in the distance estimation based on input features. The RandF model is robust to over-fitting, especially in datasets with noise or high dimensionality.
- 4) Support Vector Machine (SVM): With appropriate kernels, this model is effective for mapping the input data to distances, especially in cases with a non-linear relationship between features and the Euclidean distance.

The ED prediction evaluation between models can be performed by using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and tolerance metric ϵ , which quantifies the numerical error between the predicted position P' and the actual position P . The tolerance metric is defined as:

$$\epsilon = |P - P'|. \quad (9)$$

An additional task was conducted utilising the above-mentioned models to estimate the orientation of the node.

2) *Stage 2: 2D positioning of LIoT*: The objective of the 2nd stage is to determine the best-performing ML model for enhanced 2D positioning. The predicted Euclidean distances from stage 1 were used as an additional feature along with PV cells, and optical signal receivers readings to train DNN models. The designed DNN models can be described as follows:

- 1) Input Layer: Accepts the vector or matrix with input shape consisting of PV cells, optical signal receivers, orientation, and predicted Euclidean distances.
- 2) Hidden Layers: A range of 4 to 6 dense layers with activation functions capture the spatial relationships among the input features.
- 3) Output Layer: Two neurons output the predicted (x, y) coordinates of the node's position.

3) *Orientation prediction*: The prediction of the orientation of a LIoT node is considered to be a classification problem and involves determining the directional position of the reference side based on various input features. The voltage readings from the side PV cells vary significantly with their orientation relative to the OAP, making it crucial to capture these fluctuations for accurate predictions. By adding features such as RXs readings and the predicted ED, the performance and accuracy of the ML models can be enhanced. The performance of several widely used classification models, including the RandF classifier, DT classifier, SVM classifier, and KNN, was evaluated to determine the most suitable model for orientation prediction. This comparative analysis offers a comprehensive understanding of the strengths and limitations of each model, specifically within the context of orientation prediction for LIoT nodes.

IV. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

In order to evaluate the proposed LIoT localisation concept, a proof-of-concept prototype system was developed. The prototype implementation follows a similar approach as in our previous work [16]. The prototype is based on the infrared RC5 communication protocol, which was utilised

Fig. 3. Prototype schematics: a) prototype OAP with four OSD for multi-directional optical signal reception and DOA determination. b) the prototype node. c) the switching circuit used in the prototype node.

in the previous work. The energy-autonomous LIoT node prototype consisted of five individual PV cells, implemented on each of the five interfaces. The OAP included four OSDs (RX1 to RX4) to obtain the DoAs of the uplink signal from the node.

A. OAP prototype Implementation

The schematic of the OAP prototype is illustrated in Fig. 3a. The prototype OAP consists of one dedicated Arduino Nano board for the transmitter circuit and four Arduino Nano boards for the multi-directional receivers. The transmitter circuit uses a MOSFET to drive the attached 12W white LED array based on the modulated signal. A bias voltage was provided through a diode to drive the MOSFET, ensuring that the data transmission remained flicker-free to the human eye [7]. Each receiver board is connected to a KY-022 optical signal receiver module to detect optical signals from multi-directions. If the received signal strength is above the detectable threshold (internally fixed by the manufacturer) of the KY-022 receiver, the signal is converted into a Transistor-Transistor Logic (TTL) voltage signal by the receiver module and sent to the digital input pin of the corresponding Arduino Nano board for fast demodulation and decoding. Finally, the decoded data is transmitted to a computer via USB cables for analysis in a MATLAB environment, along with the identification information of the detector for each received IR data frame.

B. Node prototype Implementation

The schematic of the energy autonomous LIoT node prototype for the purposed localisation approach is illustrated in Fig. 3b. The prototype node utilised an Arduino Pro-Mini 3.3V 8 MHz board, with both the indicator LED and power regulators disabled for low-power optimisation. For the EHU, the system employed an Epishine EK01LEH3-6 module, with

Fig. 4. Prototype system : (a) External view of the prototype LIoT node. (b) Internal view of the LIoT node. (c) 8×14 test grid and OAP location. (d) OAP with four OSD (e) 10×10 cm size node placement on the grid.

an AEM10941 Power Management Integrated Circuit (PMIC) featuring Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) capability, a CAP-XX GA230F 0.4F Supercapacitor (SC) for energy storage, and a TPS62740 DC-DC converter for output regulation. The node's primary sensing component was a TMP36GT9Z temperature sensor. The EHU used five Epishine LEH3-50x50-6-10 printed Organic PV (OPV) cells, positioned on each side of the node's surfaces. To support multi-directional communication, the uplink used four PCB0100 dual-channel infrared transmitter modules. PV switching was achieved by using five MOSFETs (Q1 - Q5) paired with voltage dividers (Fig. 3c). When a TTL high signal is applied to the MOSFET gate, the corresponding PV cell is connected to the MCU for ADC measurement for localisation purposes. Conversely, when the gate voltage is TTL low, the MOSFET disconnects the voltage divider, fully connecting the PV cell for EH, thereby minimising interference with the EH process. A view of the implemented prototype LIoT node is shown in Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b. The algorithm of the node utilised an energy-aware approach, employing MOSFET (Q6) to connect the SC for measurement by reducing the voltage to an ADC measurable range. The energy-aware algorithm implemented in the node is illustrated in Fig. 5. In this algorithm, the node remains in standby mode until it receives an interrupt signal, which transitions it to active mode to decode the incoming message and execute the required actions. If the node does not meet the energy threshold, determined by the SC's voltage level, it enters a deep sleep mode, where it operates with minimal power consumption to conserve energy. During this period, it continues to store excess energy until sufficient levels are reached to execute commands, as defined by the threshold.

C. ML application

Fig. 5. Energy-aware prototype algorithm controlling the node through stages of deep sleep, standby, sensing, processing, and transmission.

The OAP utilises two ML models for two-stage 2D positioning of the LIoT node. The primary model was used to estimate the distance between the node and OAP. Then 2nd model predicts the node position. ED was predicted using four ML models: LR, DT, RandF, and SVM, selected based on MI analysis. Predictions from the most accurate model were used in the next stage. Also, orientation prediction via classification ML models was performed as separated action. Data pre-processing is an essential step in a ML model training, and the following steps were undertaken.

1) *Aggregation of sensor data*: calculation of the mean PV cell for every measurement, which contributed to the reduction of data noise and variability and the creation of more consistent and realistic ML model features.

2) *Normalisation*: Both PV cell and RX (OSD) values were normalised by the Min-Max scale to ensure a compatible scale. This method scales the data so that it falls within a specific range, typically $[0, 1]$, as described by (10)

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)}. \quad (10)$$

3) *Orientation One-Hot encoding*: In order to convert orientation values into numeric features, the orientation vector $O = [O_{North}, O_{East}, O_{South}, O_{West}]$ was encoded by assigning each O_i by:

$$O_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the orientation is } i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $i \in \text{North, East, South, West}$

4) *Label encoding*: The original labels of grids were represented in alphabetical order along the x-axis. Each grid label was converted into (x,y) coordinates. The dataset S was divided into training and testing subsets for each stage, with 80% of the data allocated for training and 20% for testing. The input data for the ED prediction consisted of the following features:

$$S = \{PV_1, PV_2, PV_3, PV_4, PV_5, PV_{Avg.}, RX_1, RX_2, RX_3, RX_4\}. \quad (12)$$

5) *DNN models for positioning*: Stage 2 of 2D positioning led to the development of three distinct DNN models, which were used to investigate the most efficient solution. The architecture of the proposed DNN models given in Table I.

TABLE I
ARCHITECTURE OF DNN MODELS

Layers & Output shape	DNN1	DNN2	CNN
1	Flatten; 60	Flatten; 60	Conv; 4,15,32
2	Dense; 64	Dense; 288	MaxPooling; 2,7,32
3	Dense; 64	Dense; 72	Conv; 2,7,64
4	Dense; 64	Dense; 18	MaxPooling; 1,3,64
5	Dense; 64	Dense; 9	Flatten; 192
6	Dense; 64	Dense; 2	Dense; 128
7	Dense; 64		Dropout; 128
8	Dense; 2		Dense; 64
9			Dense; 2
Total # of parameters	74504	119645	155720

1) Fully Connected Neural Network (NN):

Two fully connected DNNs were designed, both sharing identical input and output layers. The input shape is defined as (4,15), representing 15 features: 6 PV cell values, 4 RX values, 4 orientation values, and distance. The output layer consists of 2 linear activation functions. The first DNN1 consists of 6 fully connected dense layers with 64 neurons using on each layer. The second DNN2 is represented by 4 hidden dense layers with a gradual decrease in the number of neurons (288,72,18,9). The activation function is Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) for the hidden layers to introduce non-linearity. Models were compiled with the Adam optimiser, often chosen for its efficient convergence behaviour, using a RMSE loss function. Models were also configured with an early stopping mechanism to halt training if the validation loss did not improve after 20 epochs, avoiding over-fitting. These models were trained with a relatively large batch size of 64 and set to train for up to 1000 epochs.

2) Convolutional NN (CNN): The input data was reshaped to (4, 15, 1) to provide the CNN layers with a 2D structure. This model starts with two convolutional layers with 32 and 64 filters, respectively, each with a kernel size of 3x3. These layers use padding to preserve the input dimensions and apply a ReLU activation function. The output from each convolutional layer is down-sampled using max-pooling layers with pool size 2x2, effectively reducing the dimensionality and focusing on key features. After flattening, the model has two dense layers, with a dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 between them to mitigate overfitting. This model also uses the Adam optimiser, early stopping (with patience of 20 epochs), and RMSE loss function.

6) *Orientation prediction*: RandF, DT, SVM, and KNN classifier ML models were evaluated using six PV voltage values, including the average, four RX values, and predicted ED values, totaling eleven normalised features. The orientation values were encoded as numerical integers in the range of 1-4. The performance of these four popular classification models was evaluated using GridSearchCV for hyperparameter tuning. The hyperparameters optimised for each model are given in Table II. This comprehensive evaluation identified the best-performing model for accurately predicting the orientation of the LIoT node.

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETERS TUNED FOR CLASSIFICATION MODELS USING GRIDSEARCHCV

Model	Tuned Hyperparameters
RandF	- <i>n_estimators</i> : {50, 100, 200} - <i>max_depth</i> : {None, 10, 20} - <i>min_samples_split</i> : {2, 5, 10}
KNN	- <i>n_neighbors</i> : {3, 5, 7} - <i>weights</i> : {'uniform', 'distance'}
SVM	- <i>C</i> : {0.1, 1, 10} - <i>kernel</i> : {'linear', 'rbf', 'poly'}
DT	- <i>max_depth</i> : {None, 5, 10} - <i>min_samples_split</i> : {2, 5, 10}

Fig. 6. Illumination distribution measured with a lux meter over the test grid.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The test grid and the prototype system used for the experiment are depicted in Fig. 4c. The prototype node consumed 0.8 mW in standby mode and 0.08 mW in deep sleep mode. This kept its power usage below the harvesting rate of 0.5 mW (at 500 lux per single PV surface, as specified in the data sheet), ensuring energy-autonomous operation under average illumination. The evaluation grid consisted of 8×14 test points across a white background area.

A. Experimental dataset acquisition

The node was placed at each grid point, and the PV surface voltage was measured under four different orientations, with the node rotated 90 degrees for each measurement. PV surface I was used as the reference direction when measuring the four different orientations, designated as North, East, South, and West. The OAP was placed 0.6 meters above the test grid and positioned asymmetrically to create areas with different surface reflections. At each grid point, the prototype LIoT node operated energy-autonomously, relying entirely on energy harvested from the OAP's illumination. Notably, all PV voltage data at each surface were measured in parallel with the ongoing EH process and the collection of temperature sensor readings. The illumination distribution was measured using a CA 1110 lux-meter, and the corresponding grid arrangement is shown in Fig. 6. In the OAP setup, as the KY 022 OSD provides only TTL output, the detector registering the highest number of transmissions was used to determine the DOA of the node's uplink signal.

Fig. 7. Dataset: Node's PV voltage variation at each position within the test grid, with different orientations. Variations in the dominant receiver coverage areas among four optical signal receivers for each node orientation is shown on the right.

Fig. 8. Mutual Information of features for Euclidean distance prediction.

B. Dataset

The sample dataset acquired from the node's PV cells and the OAP's OSDs is presented in Fig. 7. According to the dataset, PV surface 5, corresponding to the top PV cell of the prototype node, shows no significant variation across different node orientations. The other four PV cells exhibit similar patterns based on orientation, confirming that all PV cells functioned as expected within the same voltage ranges. The dominant receiver coverage across various node orientations indicates that each receiver detects a similar DoA based on the node's position, confirming alignment between the OAP's OSD and the node's multiple transmitters within the test coverage area. Due to slight asymmetry in the prototype node, some areas overlap with adjacent receiver coverage zones. However, the receiver coverage maps still show four distinct areas corresponding to each detector's face direction.

C. Position prediction

Fig. 8 illustrates the MI scores of normalised PV cells voltage and RX readings for predicting the ED of the LiOT node to the OAP. The normalised average PV cell voltage demonstrates the highest MI score. In comparison to the previous work results [16], the performance of the RandF model is still considered to be the most accurate for distance prediction, and ED prediction accuracy was improved by more than 30% (2 cm reduction at 80%), Fig. 9a. Also, the RandF model RMSE was reduced to 4.8 at 20 cm and resulted in the lowest value, Fig. 9b. The predicted distance from the RandF model was chosen as a feature to train DNN models. Training of the DNN and CNN models resulted in the evaluation of

Fig. 9. Comparison of model performance under varying tolerance levels for Euclidean distance prediction: (a) Accuracy vs tolerance and (b) RMSE vs tolerance.

validation loss and the number of epochs, Fig. 10a. Training of models to predict a 2D position of the node was done by using normalised values of 15 features. Note, that the RMSE of DNN models are quite similar, DNN1 resulted in 6.408 with 201 epochs and DNN2 got 6.678 with 348 epochs, whereas the CNN model performed 7.861 with 172 epochs. Based on the training results, it can be concluded that CNN demonstrated the most efficient training performance. Additionally, a RandF model was trained on the same data, yielding an RMSE of 10.207, highlighting the accuracy advantage of the DNN models. Regarding the prediction accuracy, the tolerance metric was used against RMSE to visualise the performance of the proposed models. Fig. 10b illustrates that the DNN1 and DNN2 models achieved 80% accuracy at 12.5 cm, which is over 40% higher than the accuracy of the RandF model trained solely on PV cell values, in previous work [16]. Notably, the DNN1 model achieved 100% prediction accuracy within a tolerance of 15 cm. Fig. 11 illustrates the prediction accuracy of end-to-end models trained on raw features, showing that the DNN1 model achieves 100% prediction accuracy only at a tolerance of 25 cm, which is significantly lower than the performance of the two-stage approach. This result further highlights the superiority of the proposed two-stage method in this study.

D. Orientation prediction

The obtained results for the orientation prediction are illustrated in Fig. 12. The results from GridSearchCV indicate that the RandF classifier model outperformed the other models, achieving the best performance with a max_depth of 20 and 50 estimators. As shown in Fig. 12a, the RandF model achieved an accuracy of 68% against the closest competitor DT classifier with 60% prediction accuracy. The RandF model generally has enhanced robustness against overfitting, especially for the datasets with noise. The confusion matrix for the RandF model, depicted in Fig. 12b, reveals that the North orientation was predicted with the highest accuracy. This can be attributed to the lower voltage values observed on the PV cells when oriented towards the North. PV voltage saturation occurred in grids near the OAP, introducing increased variability and

Fig. 10. Performance comparison of models for position prediction: (a) Loss versus epochs for DNN, CNN models training, and (b) Position accuracy with tolerance for DNN, CNN, and RandF models.

Fig. 11. Positioning accuracy vs. tolerance for end-to-end DNN, CNN, and RandF models trained on raw features.

randomness in orientation predictions in these areas, which made accurate orientation predictions more challenging. In future work, these challenges could be mitigated by refining voltage variation patterns during the node implementation stage.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research presents an ML-assisted 2D positioning approach for battery-free, energy-autonomous LIoT sensor networks, offering a sustainable solution that integrates positioning, orientation awareness, and EH functionalities. By repurposing OSDs at OAPs and PV energy harvesters at nodes, a proof-of-concept prototype was developed to validate the proposed system design. The transparent node casing and optimised indoor OPV configuration minimised voltage variation, enabling consistent performance. A two-stage ML-assisted localisation framework was employed, combining a RandF regression model for ED estimation with a DNN for precise 2D positioning. This hybrid approach achieved 80% accuracy within a 12.5 cm tolerance, demonstrating a 37.5% improvement over prior work under similar conditions. Additionally, the proposed orientation prediction method achieved

Fig. 12. Variation in (a) orientation prediction accuracies across models and (b) confusion matrix for the RandF classifier.

68% accuracy, with challenges near OAPs due to voltage saturation and increased variability. While the two-stage approach demonstrates superior accuracy, errors in stage 1, such as systematic biases in the RandF model, may propagate to stage 2, as the RandF-predicted ED is a critical feature for coordinate estimation. Future work could focus on tracking and compensating for these errors to minimise their impact on later stages and further improve positioning accuracy. For scalability, which is essential for real-world deployment, a clustered single-OAP approach, combined with multi-OAP coordination, spatial diversity, and OSD data fusion, can enhance localisation accuracy and mitigate OAP illumination overlap. Furthermore, integrating PV cell current measurements, which are more sensitive to illumination variations, can further improve positioning precision. In order to mitigate issues such as PV cell saturation, future refinements will focus on hardware-level improvements, including PV current-based measurements and the integration of multiple smaller PV cells with equivalent power generation to enhance dataset diversity. Additionally, integrating real-time adaptive ML methods, such as reinforcement learning and historical data analysis, can improve positioning and orientation accuracy by adapting to mobility, shadowing, and illumination variations. The proposed localisation approach is not limited to LIoT systems but can be broadly applicable to any intermittent operating, battery-free IoT devices equipped with multiple energy harvesters and directional receivers. By integrating localisation functionality, LIoT systems achieve simultaneous communication, EH, and position awareness using the same OAP illumination source, all while operating energy autonomously. This contribution points toward next-generation sustainable sensor networks where functionality and sustainability are seamlessly integrated.

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